

The Boy Who Cried Wolf Effect and the Paradox It Causes

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The Boy Who Cried Wolf effect is the classic tale, in which the shepherd lies to the village repeatedly that the wolf is coming but this is not true, and the village stops believing him. But one day when the wolf really comes, the shepherd warns again, the village ignores him. And the wolf ends up eating all his sheep.

But this is only one side of the coin. Then it occurred to me to see it as a bias, and make the Reverse Psychology version. I called it The Inverse Boy Who Cried Wolf Effect.

It goes like this: The little shepherd has an objective, that the wolf attacks the village. But to do so, he repeatedly says that the wolf is coming but this is not true, and the village stops believing him. But one day when the wolf really comes, the shepherd warns again, the village ignores him. And instead of the wolf eating the sheep, the wolf goes to the village and causes a disaster, because they did not believe him.

Even if you do not believe it, this reverse psychology technique is more effective than you think. Let us suppose a person X is wanted by the government for inventing something that is not convenient for them. Then person X, knowing this, decides to publish all their progress even if it is incomplete, or does not work, but all the ways in which they have tried to build this. The government, analyzing everything, will stop paying attention. And even if they do pay attention, it would be VERY difficult to see which of all of those is the good one and the one that works.

Let us suppose the government realizes this. So they adopt the tactic of taking this seriously, but how could they differentiate a case of the Inverse Boy Who Cried Wolf effect from everything being false? Of all the attempts only 1 makes the difference. First, if they all have the same title. It would be too tedious to go through them 1 by 1, and by Occam's Razor they will prefer to believe the simplest option, that all are false because the majority are, instead of that only 1 is the correct one.

If any counterintelligence or intelligence organization suspects me for creating this document, by Occam's Razor they could neither prove nor refute that what

I say makes me a suspect.

Tautologically it is impossible to know which is correct, both are correct at the same time. I am a suspect and not a suspect at the same time, and both are absolute truths.

The NSA, possibly upon seeing my P=NP papers, fell into my trap, but the question is, is the trap that I did it to distract them and publish the real P=NP, or is the trap that I did it to distract them and not have the real P=NP? Even if I state the real motive here, you will not believe me because of Occam's Razor.

Is the bias the preference for the known, or is it the preference for trying to avoid the bias? And how do we know which one it is?

Is the true objective of this paper to demonstrate the truth, or to demonstrate a falsehood as a truth? In itself it is an infinite recursion loop. All of this is false. "It could be that what I say is true, or it could be that I made this paper with reverse psychology with the intention that you believe that what I say could be the truth, or it could be that I made this paper with reverse psychology with the intention that you believe that 'it could be that I made this paper with reverse psychology with the intention that you believe that what I say could be the truth,' or it could be that I made this paper for the following intention: 'it could be that I made this paper with reverse psychology with the intention that you believe that it could be that I made this paper with reverse psychology with the intention that you believe that what I say could be the truth'" but truly the truth is the inverse."